

ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES OF SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART IV.

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The adsorption of homologous series of mono- and dibasic aliphatic acids by acid- and alkali-condensed phenolic resins, amino- and protein resins has been studied. The reversal of Traube's rule in the case of alkali-condensed, amino- and protein resins is explained on the basis of orientation of molecules at the resin-solvent surface according to the theory put forward by Langmuir and Harkins. The influence of various substituents on adsorption has also been studied. The adsorption by ammonia-condensed amino- and protein resins increases with the introduction of COOH, OH, CN, Cl, Br. The NH₂ and alkyl groups cause a decrease in adsorption.

The results obtained in the case of acid phenolic resins are quite the opposite to those in basic resins. This is probably due to the fact that acid resin is less polar than water. In non-polar solvents results are in line with those obtained in basic resins.

Bhatnagar, Kapur and Puri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 679) have shown that the order of adsorption of organic acids in a homologous series by acid-condensed phenolic resins follows Traube's rule. S. Tsuruta (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1938, **41**, 129B) found that the order of the series was reversed when ammonia-condensed resins were used as adsorbents. This was also confirmed by observations in this laboratory and an explanation was given in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 261) on the basis of the pores of the resin. It was shown that the adsorption of the acids by amino- or ammonia-condensed resins increased as the ionisation constant increased and the reverse holds good for acid-condensed phenolic resin. The present work has been undertaken to throw more light on this subject and to give a possible explanation which may account for all the facts. These reversals are known to occur in the case of gold (Heymann and Boye, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, **59**, 153) and silica gel (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 522). Heymann and Boye (*loc. cit.*) studied the adsorption of acetic, propionic, butyric and caproic acids from water, CCl₄, C₆H₆, alcohol, and acetone by metallic gold and experienced the reversal of Traube's rule. This was explained by the fact that the highly polar group—COOH in solution oriented towards polar gold particles and the non-polar alkyl part towards the solvent. Since with the increase of the hydrocarbon chain the molecule becomes less polar, the higher fatty acids are therefore less adsorbed by gold. The adsorption of various aliphatic acids has been studied and attempts have been made to

explain the amounts adsorbed on considerations based on polarity of the resin, the solvent, and the adsorbate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Resins.

Amino- and Phenolic Resins.—Amino- and phenolic resins were prepared as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

Protein Resins.—The powdered soyabean meal was stirred into a 10% solution of sodium chloride at 40° and filtered through glass wool. The protein was precipitated from the milky suspension by the addition of dilute acetic acid. A colourless precipitate was obtained on standing. This was filtered, washed with methyl alcohol till free from chloride ions, acetic acid and starch.

10 G. of dried protein thus prepared, were refluxed with 60 c.c. of formalin (40% formaldehyde) for 2 to 3 hours. It was then filtered, washed with hot water until free from formaldehyde. The resin was dried and sieved through 100 mesh.

Adsorption Experiments.—The adsorption experiments were carried out in stoppered glass bottles which were thoroughly cleaned, steamed and dried. The powdered resin (1 g.) was weighed out in each bottle and 100 c.c. of the aqueous solutions of the acids were run in. The bottles were vigorously shaken for 5 minutes and set aside for 36 hours to attain equilibrium. The supernatant solution (10 c.c.) was pipetted out and run into excess of standard sodium hydroxide solution. The equilibrium concentration (C_e in millimoles per litre) was determined by titrating the excess of caustic soda against standard hydrochloric acid. Blank experiments were run side by side which gave the original concentration (C_0 in millimoles per litre). The difference ($C_0 - C_e$) gave the amount adsorbed (X , in millimoles per g. of the resin) from 100 c.c. of the aqueous solutions.

TABLE I.

% Sorption of monocarboxylic acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 *M* aqueous solution.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formalin resins.		<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine-formaldehyde resin.	Protein-formaldehyde resin.
	HCl condensed.	NH ₃ condensed.		
Formic	3.32%	20.04%	33.65%	3.32%
Acetic	5.50	13.00	31.5	1.00
Butyric	8.11	12.18	22.84	0.00

TABLE II.

% Sorption of acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their solution in benzene.

Acids	Resorcinol-formalin resins.		<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine-formaldehyde resins.	Protein resins.
	HCl-condensed.	NH ₃ -condensed.		
Formic	33.7%	63.8%	87.4%	30.0%
Acetic	20.7	40.0	54.6	19.0
Butyric	18.0	35.2	48.6	16.0

TABLE III.

% Sorption of acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their solution in carbon tetrachloride.

Formic	52.8%	84.5%	97.7%	42.6%
Acetic	40.7	65.5	73.8	30.7
Butyric	32.1	52.08	61.5	26.0

TABLE IV.

% Sorption of acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their solution in chloroform.

Formic	13.8%	31.0%	78.1%	10.0%
Acetic	10.7	25.8	46.2	8.6
Butyric	9.5	11.5	18.4	4.5

TABLE V.

% Sorption of acids by 1 g. of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin (acid-condensed) from various solvents.

Solvents.	Dipole moments* of the acids.	→			
		Water.	CHCl ₃ .	C ₆ H ₆ .	CCl ₄ .
*Dipole moments of the solvents × 10 ¹⁰		1.85	0.95	0.2	0
Formic	1.45%	3.3%	13.8%	33.0%	52.8%
Acetic	1.04	5.5	10.7	20.7	40.7
Butyric	0.93	8.1	9.5	18.0	32.1

* The values for dipole moments have been taken from *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930., B10, 220.

An examination of Tables I to V shows that

(1) In aqueous solutions the adsorption of a homologous series of fatty acids on acid phenolic resins follows the normal order. But in basic phenolic resins and amino-resins the order is reversed (Table I).

(2) In non-polar solvents the Traube's rule is reversed even in the case of acid phenolic resins (Tables II, III and IV).

(3) As the dipole moment of the solvent decreases the percentage sorption increases, the sorption being maximum in the case of carbon tetrachloride which has a zero moment.

All the above facts can be easily explained on the Langmuir-Harkins theory of surface orientation if we assume that the acid phenolic resins are less polar than water and the basic phenolic resins and the amino-resins are more polar than water. In support of this we have the observation of Megson and Drummond (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1930, **49**, 251T) who found that when phenol and formaldehyde are condensed in presence of an acid 2 : 4-di-hydroxyphenylmethane

is formed. While using an alkaline catalyst hydroxybenzyl alcohols () are formed. Pollak and Riesenfeld (*Z. angew. Chem.*,

1930, **43**, 1129) have found that by the basic condensation of phenol and formaldehyde, the benzyl alcohols formed gives low molecular products which have a strongly polar character.

According to Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 2221) and Harkins (*ibid.*, 1917, **39**, 354) the surface tension phenomena in general are dependent upon the orientation and packing of the molecules in surface layers and the forces involved in that action are related to those involved in solution and adsorption.

The presence of one of the strongly polar groups such as -OH, -CHO, -COOH, in molecules confers on them the property of solubility in a polar solvent like water. As the length of the hydrocarbon chain increases the solubility of the molecule markedly decreases. The diminution in solubility is probably not due to any weakening of the force of attraction between the water and the polar group. The active groups such -OH, -COOH, -Br, -Cl strive to penetrate the surface of water and do so provided that the hydrocarbon residue is not too large. If the hydrocarbon chain is too long, the attractive force between the polar group and the polar water, though still the same as before, is not sufficient to pull the long chain into the water. So, the polar group is oriented towards and possibly dissolved in the water, whereas the hydrocarbon chain points away and is out of the

water surface and so dissolution is prevented. Bartell and Millar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, **28**, 992) also came to similar conclusions from their results on the adsorption of organic acids on carbon.

Now in a basic resin-water interface, the resin is more polar than water and the fatty acid molecules will orient themselves so that the polar -COOH group is oriented towards the more polar resin surface and the non-polar alkyl group is oriented towards water. As we ascend the homologous series, though the force between the polar surface and the end -COOH group remains constant, the long hydrocarbon chain becomes increasingly difficult to pull into the polar surface. The molecule therefore has a tendency to go more into water or at least to assume a tilted position. Thus it will take more of the resin surface in the tilted position than if it were in the vertical position. Hence lesser number of molecules will be adsorbed with increase in molecular weight. This explains the reversal of Traube's rule in alkali-catalysed resins. Further, as is well known in the case of fatty acids, the molecular association decreases with the increase in hydrocarbon chain. So there are greater possibilities for the packing effect due to superimposition of the carboxylic groups in the lower fatty acids than in their less associating higher homologues because in the latter case the molecules will cover more of the resin surface. Therefore, we should expect a decrease in adsorption with increase in molecular weight as has been observed.

In the case of an acid-catalysed phenolic resin, it being less polar than water, the polar -COOH group will tend to orient more towards water. In the case of higher homologues, though the force between water and the polar -COOH group is constant, it is more difficult to pull the longer chain into water and the balance of distribution of the acid between water and the resin shifts towards the resin. So we should expect results opposite to those obtained in the case of basic resins *i.e.*, the adsorption increases with increase of molecular weight.

This view is further supported by the results tabulated in Table VI. In ammonia-condensed and amino-resins the adsorption of the *cis*-form is greater than that of the *trans*-form.

When both the carboxylic groups are oriented towards the resin surface, the substance should be expected to get adsorbed more than when only one is oriented towards it. The adsorption of citraconic acid is greater than that of fumaric acid but less than that of malic acid due to the decrease of polarity by the introduction of the positive $-\text{CH}_3$ group. The order of adsorption is reversed in the case of acid-condensed resin as was to be expected.

TABLE VI.

% Sorption of the acids by 1 g. of the resin from 100 c.c. of 0.01M-soln.

Acids.	Constitution.	Protein formaldehyde resin.	<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine-formalin resin.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.	
				NH ₃ -catalysed.	HCl-catalysed.
Fumaric	$\begin{array}{c} \text{H}-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \\ \parallel \\ \text{COOH}-\text{C}-\text{H} \end{array}$	15.35%	71.43%	26.73%	2.57%
Malic	$\begin{array}{c} \text{H}-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \\ \parallel \\ \text{H}-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \end{array}$	32.33	80.70	43.36	2.00
Citraconic	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \\ \parallel \\ \text{H}-\text{C}-\text{COOH} \end{array}$	27.00	74.90	36.61	2.20

TABLE VII.

% Sorption of acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c. c. of their 0.01M-aq. soln.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.		<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine resin.	Protein resin	Ionisation constant.
	HCl catalysed.	NH ₃ catalysed.			
Formic	3.3%	20.04%	33.65%	3.3%	2.14×10^{-4}
Acetic	5.5	13.00	31.50	1.0	1.86×10^{-5}
Butyric	8.1	11.42	22.84	—	1.48×10^{-5}
Oxalic	1.75	34.60	74.40	25.00	3.80×10^{-2}
Malonic	2.27	24.40	68.30	14.83	1.61×10^{-3}
Succinic	2.85	16.30	47.20	3.00	6.6×10^{-5}
Aconitic	1.00	26.51	80.00	19.10	1.33×10^{-2}

Table VII shows the sorption of mono-, di-, and tricarboxylic acid by acid- and alkali-catalysed phenolic resins, *m*-phenylenediamine and protein resins. In the previous paper an explanation for the order of adsorption was given on the basis of the ionisation constant of the acid and on the accomodability of the molecule in the capillary structure of the resin. Although this view explained satisfactorily the order of adsorption in a homologous series, but it will be clear from an examination of Table VII that there is no general relation between the ionisation constants and adsorbability when members of different series are taken into account *e.g.* why oxalic and malonic acids having much greater ionisation constants than formic, acetic and butyric acids should have lesser adsorption in acidic

resins. This discrepancy can be easily explained on the polar concept. The dibasic acids having two polar groups would have greater tendency to get oriented towards the more polar water than towards the comparatively small polar resin surface. It is interesting to note that the adsorption of oxalic and malonic acids in ammonia-catalysed and *m*-phenylenediamine resins is almost double that of formic and acetic acids respectively. This is probably due to the fact that each of the latter acids differs from the former in having one hydrogen replaced by a -COOH group. The addition of another -COOH group would naturally be expected to give an equal increment to adsorption. They will, therefore, have lesser adsorption in acid resins as already explained. Aconitic acid having three polar carboxyl groups is adsorbed least of all.

From Table VIII it is clear that as more polar groups are introduced in the molecule, the adsorption also increases in ammonia-condensed and amino-resins, while it decreases in an acid-condensed resin.

The polarisability due to orientation is given by $\mu^2/3kT$ where μ is the dipole moment, k is the Planck's constant and T , the absolute temperature. In our experiments T and K remain constant. Therefore the greater the

TABLE VIII.

% Sorption of substituted acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 *M* aq. soln.

Acids	Resorcinol-form- aldehyde resin.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene- diamine resin.	Protein resin.	Ionisation constant.	Dipole moment of groups $\times 10^{18}$.	
	Acid con- densed.	NH ₂ condensed.				
Acetic	5.5	13.0	31.50	1.0	1.85×10^{-5}	—
Chloroacetic	2.05	30.69	62.50	12.9	1.52×10^{-3}	2.0
Dichloroacetic	1.30	40.88	77.46	30.05	5.00×10^{-2}	4.0
Trichloroacetic	—	42.15	82.55	33.96	2.00×10^{-1}	6.0
Cyanoacetic	1.94	33.50	67.00	14.56	3.56×10^{-3}	3.5
Hydroxyacetic (glycollic)	2.30	18.81	35.64	2.40	1.51×10^{-4}	1.7
Aminoacetic (gly- cocol)	13.5	0.0	2.5	0.0	3.40×10^{-10}	1.3
Propionic	5.5	13.0	31.5	1.00	1.40×10^{-5}	—
Chloropropionic	9.0	20.39	49.52	6.50	1.47×10^{-3}	2.0
Hydroxypro- pionic (lactic)	13.8	16.00	33.50	2.00	1.38×10^{-4}	1.7
Aminopropionic	35.5	9.70	16.10	—	9.00×10^{-10}	1.3

* The values for the dipole moments for the groups are taken from "The Dipole moments and Chemical Structure" by Debye.

dipole moment, the greater would be the polarisation. The dipole moment will in its turn depend on the moments of the groups introduced. Hence the greater the moment of the group, the greater will be the polarisability in the substituted acids. In case of ammonia-condensed and amino-resins the percentage adsorption increases with the increase of group moments, which is as should be expected. Thus we see that in the case of substituted acids also the polar view holds good. Since NH_2 group has a moment opposite to that of other groups, the decrease of adsorption in the case of amino-acids is also explained satisfactorily.

TABLE IX.

% Sorption of ketonic acids by 1 g. of the resin from their 100 c.c. of 0.01M-aq. soln.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.		<i>m</i> -Phenylene-diamine resin.	Protein resin.
	Acid-con-densed.	NH_3 -con-densed.		
Pyruvic (acetoformic)	3.14%	32.50%	55.0%	18.0%
Laevalinic (acetopropionic)	10.50	13.80	34.0	—

From Table IX it is clear that the percentage adsorption of ketonic acids also increases with increase of molecular weight in the case of acid-condensed resin, while the reverse holds good in the case of ammonia-condensed and amino-resins.

TABLE X.

% Sorption of substituted succinic acids by 1 g. of resins from 100 c.c. of their 0.01M aq. soln.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resins.		<i>m</i> -Phenylene-diamine resin.	Protein resin.	Group moment $\times 10^{18}$.
	Acid-con-densed.	NH_3 -con-densed.			
Succinic	2.85%	16.3%	47.20%	8.0%	—
Dibromosuccinic	—	25.0	61.10	23.47	3.8
Malic	2.00	16.66	48.30	8.16	1.7
Tartaric	0.75	18.34	52.0	10.10	3.4
Aminosuccinic	15.61	11.2	14.1	2.44	1.3

Table X shows the effect on adsorption of succinic acid of the introduction of different groups. It will be seen that as in the case of substituted acetic acids, the introduction of halide and hydroxyl groups increases the adsorption in basic resins and decreases it in acidic resins. The amino group having an opposite polarity causes reverse results in both the resins.

From Table XI we find that with the introduction of OH and carboxylic groups the adsorption increases. The adsorption is increased to a greater extent by the COOH group than by the OH group which is as should be according to group moments.

TABLE XI.

% Sorption of hydroxy acids by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01M-aqueous solution.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.		<i>m</i> -Phenylene-diamine resin.	Protein resin.
	Acid-con-densed.	NH ₂ -con-densed.		
Lactic	13.8	16.0	33.5	—
Glycollic	2.3	18.81	35.64	2.4
Malic	2.0	16.16	48.3	8.16
Tartaric	0.75	18.84	52.0	10.1
Citric	0.50	18.22	63.05	12.8

From the above results we come to the conclusion that amino-and alkali-condensed resins behave as strongly polar substances while the acid-condensed resins behave as non-polar or weakly polar substances.

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